

AN IMPROVED ALGORITHM FOR CALCULATING THE SUM-OF-FACTORIALS FUNCTION

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Abstract The sum of factorials function, also known as the left factorial function, is defined as $!n = 0! + 1! + \dots + (n-1)!$. These have been used by Smarandache and Kurepa to define the Smarandache-Kurepa Function (see reference [1], [2]). This paper presents an effective method for calculating $!n$, and implements the Smarandache-Kurepa function by using one new method.

1. Introduction

We define $!n$ as $0! + 1! + \dots + (n-1)!$.

A simple PARI/GP program to calculate these values is below:

$$\text{soff}(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} i!$$

Then,

for($i = 0, 10, \text{print}1(", \text{soff}(i))$) gives the desired output;

0, 1, 2, 4, 10, 34, 154, 874, 5914, 46234, 409114,

which is A003422 at OEIS [3].

2. A new method

If we write out what the sum of factorials function is doing, we can write:

$$\begin{array}{r} 1+ \\ 1+ \\ 1.2+ \\ 1.2.3+ \\ 1.2.3.4+ \\ 1.2.3.4.5+ \end{array}$$

and so on.

If we now read down the columns, we see that this can be written as:

$$1 + 1[1 + 2[1 + 3[1 + 4[1 + \dots$$

This is because we have an opening 1 from $0!$. Then 1 is a factor of all the remaining factorials. However 1 is the only factor of 1 of the factorials, namely $1!$, so we have

$$1 + 1[1 + \dots]$$

Having removed the $1!$, 2 is now a factor of all remaining factorials, and is the final factor in $2!$, hence

$$1 + 1[1 + 2[1 + \dots]]$$

and so on.

$!n$ requires inputs from $0!$ to $(n - 1)!$, and hence we are required to stop the nested recursion by $n - 1$. e.g. for $!5$, we have

$$1 + 1[1 + 2[1 + 3[1 + 4[1]]]].$$

We can validate this:

$$1 + 1[1 + 2[1 + 3[1 + 4[1]]]]$$

$$= 1 + 1[1 + 2[1 + 3[5]]]$$

$$= 1 + 1[1 + 2[16]]$$

$$= 1 + 1[33]$$

$$= 34.$$

3. Code for new method

We can see how the new method decreases execution time, the original method presented performs $O(k^2)$ multiplications and $O(k)$ additions. This method performs $O(k)$ multiplications and $O(k)$ additions.

PARI/GP code for the routine is below:

```
qsoff(n) = local(r); r = n; forstep(i = n - 2, 1, 4 - 1, r* = i; r + +); r
```

4. Implementing the Smarandache-Kurepa function

We need only consider primes, and the sk variable needs only range from 1 to $p - 1$ (if $!1$ to $!p$ are not divisible by p , then $!(p + k)$ will never be as all new terms have p as a factor).

For prime ($p = 2, 500$, for ($sk = 1, p$, if ($qsoff(sk)$

This is obviously wasteful, we are calculating $qsoff(sk)$ very repetitively. The code below stores the $qsoff()$ values in a vector.

v=vector(500, i, qsoff(i)); forprime (p = 2500, for (sk = 1, p, if (v[sk]
 The following output is produced:

2, -, 4, 6, 6, -, 5, 7, 7, -, 12, 22, 16, -, -, -, -, 55, -, 54, 42, -, -, 24, -, -, 25,
 -, -, 86, -, 97, -, 133, -, -, 64, 94, 72, 58, -, -, 49, 69, 19, -, 78, -, 14, -, 208,
 167, -, 138, 80, 59, -, -, -, -, 63, 142, 41, -, 110, 22, 286, 39, -, 84, -, -, 215, 80,
 14, 305, -, 188, 151, 53, 187, -, 180, -, -, -, -, 44, 32, 83, 92, -, 300, 16, -.

5. Additional relations

The basic pattern created in this paper also allows for the rapid calculation of other Smarandache-like functions based on the sum of factorials function.

For example, we could define $SSF(n)$ as the sum of squares factorial, e.g. $SSF(10) = 0! + 1! + 4! + 9!$, and the corresponding general expansion is

$$1 + 1[1 + 2.3.4[1 + 5.6.7.8.9[1 + \dots .$$

Or we can define the sum of factorials squared function as

$$0!^2 + 1!^2 + 2!^2 + \dots .$$

In this case, the expansion is

$$1 + 1[1 + 4[1 + 9[1 + \dots .$$

References

[1] Smarandache-Kurepa Function: <http://www.gallup.unm.edu/smarandache/FUNCT1.TXT>

[2] Eric W. Weisstein. "Smarandache-Kurepa Function." From MathWorld—A Wolfram Web Resource. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/Smarandache-Kurepa-Function.html>

[3] OEIS : A003422 (Left factorials) <http://www.research.att.com/projects/OEIS/Anum=A003422>